

Exploring the valorisation potential of urban wastewater in Flanders by the application of a 2-stage technology

L., Dockx*, S., Moreno Sayavedra**, I., Sigurnjak**, B., Saelens*, E., Meers**, and B., De Bock*

*Aquafin NV, Dijkstraat 8, 2630 Aartselaar, Belgium, lennert.dockx@aquafin.be

**RE-SOURCE LAB, Laboratory for BioResource Recovery, Department of Green Chemistry and Technology, Faculty of Bioscience Engineering, Ghent University, Coupure Links 653, 9000 Ghent, Belgium, sarah.morenosayavedra@ugent.be

Abstract: Nitrogen (N) fixation and production of N-based fertilizers by the application of the Haber-Bosch process is associated to 1-2% of the global energy consumption. Additionally, the biological N-removal during urban wastewater (WW) treatment by application of both nitrification (conversion of NH_4^+ to NO_3^-) and denitrification (conversion of NO_3^- to N_2) is an energy demanding process and is moreover linked to additional N_2O emissions. This study aims to close nutrient cycles by exploring the potential of a 2-stage technology connecting WW treatment and agriculture needs by treatment of real domestic WW by high-rate activated sludge (HRAS) and subsequent recovery of N from the effluent using natural zeolites as adsorption material. The process demonstrated N and C-removal efficiencies, ranging from 74% to 82% and 76% to 89%, respectively. An adsorption capacity of 1.4-8.4 mg N/g of zeolites was achieved. The N-content of the regeneration liquid ranged between 25-845 mg NH_4^+ -N/L.

Keywords: ammonium recovery; fertilising product; urban wastewater;

In order to obtain a more sustainable and energy-efficient approach, steps within the conventional N-cycle should be eliminated. In Flanders (Belgium), currently 0.5-0.7% of the total electricity use is associated with urban WW transportation and treatment by the conventional activated sludge (CAS) process (0.25-0.30 kWh/m³ of treated WW). HRAS is an alternative system with a better energy balance and less emissions, but it cannot be used standalone because of the insufficient N-removal¹. Consequently, HRAS must be combined with another technology in order to meet discharge limits (European and Flemish standards) and to valorise relevant resources present in the WW. In this study, ion-exchange technology, using natural zeolites, was applied for the recovery of NH_4^+ present in the HRAS effluent².

The fully-automated pilot (1 m³/d) was operated at the WWTP of Aartselaar. After a mechanical treatment (by a coarse grid), the influent (Table 1) of the full-scale plant was redirected to the pilot without additional pre-treatment. Fluctuations in WW composition (e.g. dry/wet weather, peak loads during the morning) were taken into account, providing realistic and relevant conditions. In order to reduce the area footprint of the installation, a sequencing batch reactor, with a working volume of 378 L, was used. The secondary sludge of the full-scale plant was used as inoculum and was converted stepwise (Table 2) into a HRAS system by adapting both sludge retention time (SRT) and organic loading rate (OLR). The N-adsorption was conducted by the use of natural zeolites (aluminosilicate mineral, Na^+ and H^+ form – granular size: 0.2-1 mm). A flow range between 5 and 40 bed volumes per hour was applied. Once breakthrough was observed, a 3 w/v% KCl solution was used for the desorption of NH_4^+ , resulting in the presence of potassium (macro-nutrient) in the regeneration liquid.

Table 1. Influent characterization of the SBR pilot (HRAS) during different periods of operation at the WWTP (CAS) of Aartselaar (54,000 PE (60 gBOD/(PE.d))).

Parameter (mg/L)	Period				
	I	II	III	IV	V
BOD	83	53	94	210	150
NH ₄ -N	22	16	26	45	42
TSS	120	62	100	160	120
TN	31	21	33	58	53

Table 2. Overview of the OLR (gbCOD/(gVSS.d)) and SRT (d). Parameters were changed once steady-state conditions within a period were observed. Period I-III are defined as an adaption period.

Parameter	Period				
	I	II	III	IV	V
OLR (gbCOD/(gVSS.d))	0.4	0.4	0.7	2.5	1.8
SRT (d)	22	11	5	2	4

As shown in Figure 1, the HRAS process in contact stabilization (HRAS/CS) mode can remove organic matter and suspended solids from the wastewater with low energy input (0.4 kWh/m³) and high energy recovery from sludge (Table 3), while leaving N behind in the effluent. An adsorption capacity of 1.4-8.4 mg N/g of zeolites was achieved. The N-content of the regeneration liquid ranged between 25-845 mg NH₄⁺-N/L. Additional experiments are planned to further optimize these results.

Figure 1. Removal efficiency (in %) of BOD, NH₄, total nitrogen (TN) and suspended solids (TSS) during different periods of operation. Period I-III are defined as an adaption period.

Once HRAS conditions were achieved, sludge was analysed in order to define the biomethane potential (BMP) (Table 3). A clear increase of the BMP of the HRAS (in comparison to CAS) was observed. Despite this improvement, according to literature³, it should be possible to achieve even higher production rates.

Table 3. BMP (Nm³ CH₄/ton dry weight) of different types of sludge.

BMP (Nm ³ CH ₄ /ton dry weight)	Sludge type	
	CAS	HRAS
	125 ± 10	213 ± 17

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